

Comparative analysis of the Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor topologies and the impacts of temperature on their performance

Raymond BIRASA
Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Cluj-Napoca, Romania
raymond.birasa@emd.utcluj.ro

Claudia Steluța Marțiș
Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Cluj-Napoca, Romania
claudia.martis@emd.utcluj.ro

Abstract—This paper analyses the influence of the increased operating temperature on the performances of five PMSM topologies designed with identical general specifications and constraints. The studied topologies are Surface-mounted Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (SPMSM), Halbach Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (HPMSM), Inlet Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (IPMSM), Spoke Interior Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (SIPMSM), and V-shape Interior Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (VIPMSM). The electromagnetic torque, back-EMF, and the permanent magnet magnetic flux density are analysed for four operation temperature levels (20°C, 60°C, 100°C, and 140°C). The analysis provides insights on the aspects to be considered for further development of online detecting, locating, and quantifying the degree of PM demagnetisation in PMSM.

Keywords—demagnetisation, permanent magnet synchronous motor topology, temperature.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advantages of Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSMs) include simple excitation, compact structure, high efficiency, low inertia, and a high torque-to-volume ratio [1]-[2]. These features make PMSMs widely used in various fields, including robotics, electric vehicles, aerospace, and industrial drives [3].

The permanent magnets (PM) used in PMSMs are made up of ceramics known as ferrite, Alnico (aluminium, nickel, and cobalt), and rare earth magnets. Rare-earth magnets are made of lanthanide group element alloys. Neodymium (Nd) and samarium (Sm) are the two lanthanide elements most commonly used to manufacture permanent magnets. Numerous patents cover several rare-earth magnet alloy compositions, but the most popular types in commercial use are neodymium-iron-boron ($\text{Nd}_2\text{Fe}_{14}\text{B}$) and samarium cobalt [4], [5].

Alnico (aluminium, nickel, and cobalt) has a high Curie temperature and good temperature stability, as it also contains other metallic elements such as nickel and cobalt. Ferromagnetic materials like cobalt and nickel are characterised by their plentiful resources and affordable prices; however, their remanent flux density is relatively low, and their B_r is from 0.2T to 0.44 T [6].

NdFeB possesses high coercivity, remanence, and maximum energy product (BHmax). Despite its good performance, it has

certain drawbacks, such as poor temperature characteristics, as evidenced by its low Curie temperature and high-temperature coefficient. The lower half of the demagnetisation curve was nonlinear, and the magnetic loss increased significantly at high temperatures. The NdFeB has low-temperature stability, which causes a substantial loss of magnetic characteristics at high temperatures owing to the high irreversible loss and temperature coefficient [6].

During operation, the motor creates heat, vibration, a demagnetising magnetic field, and other effects that may cause the permanent magnet to demagnetise, reducing its operating point and performance. If demagnetisation is severe, the permanent magnet will work below the knee point, and irreversible demagnetisation will occur, resulting in a decline in the permanent magnet's performance [6], [7].

In addition to PM demagnetisation, other faults in PMSMs, such as rotor eccentricity, circuit failure, bearing failure, and vibration, affect the PMSMs' performance [7], [8]. The demagnetisation is a serious issue because it can result in reduced performance and back-EMF and an increase in the starting current, torque ripple, vibration, and acoustic noise, and the following factors can cause it [6], [7], [9]:

- High-temperature stress,
- inverse magnetic fields,
- short-circuit current,
- ageing of magnets themselves,
- vibration,
- PM oxidation,
- Corrosion,
- high stator currents caused by the inverter.

This paper examines the influence of operating temperature on the performance of five distinct PMSM topologies regarding PM behaviour. PMSM topologies were designed under the identical specifications and constraints (same stator outer diameter, number of turns per phase, air gap size, and permanent magnet volume on the rotor) without any additional optimisation procedure.

The main goal of the work is to prepare the path towards developing techniques and solutions for further online detecting, locating, and quantifying the degree of demagnetisation of PM due to operation temperature in different PMSM topologies. Preliminary analysis is conducted at the following temperature grades: 20°C, 60°C, 100°C and 140°C, and the impact of operation temperature rise on the electromagnetic torque and back-EMF is analysed.

The PMSM design, modelling, and simulation are conducted through two-dimensional finite element analysis (FEA), and the results of healthy and demagnetised motors are studied.

II. STUDIED ROTOR TOPOLOGIES, REQUIREMENTS AND MAIN DIMENSIONS

The designed and analysed rotor topologies correspond to Surface-Mounted Permanent Magnet (SPMSM), Inset Permanent Magnet (IPMSM), Halbach Permanent Magnet (HPMSM), Spoke Interior Permanent Magnet (SIPMSM), V Shape Interior Permanent Magnet (VIPMSM), as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Five types of PM rotor topologies

TABLE I. MAIN GEOMETRICAL DIMENSIONS

Main dimensions	Values and units
Stator outer diameter	102 mm
Stack height	65 mm
Rotor outer diameter	51.02 mm
Airgap thickness	0.5 mm
Rotor PM volume	15170 mm ³

TABLE II. ELECTRICAL DESIGN SPECIFICATIONS

Motor parameters	Value and Units
Rated speed	4500 rpm
Number of phases	3
Number of poles	8
Number of slots	18
Maximum DC supply voltage	72 V

All the topologies were designed using the dimensions and specifications shown in Tables I and II, respectively.

The winding configuration corresponds to 8 poles and double-layer windings, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The configuration of the stator winding diagram of PMSM

III. EVALUATION OF THE ELECTROMAGNETIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDIED CASES

The electromagnetic torque of PMSM can be written as:

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} \cdot p \cdot [\psi_{PM} \cdot i_q + (L_d - L_q) \cdot i_d \cdot i_d] \quad (1)$$

Where i_d and i_q are the d-q currents, L_d and L_q are the d-q inductances, and ψ_{PM} is the PM flux.

The back-EMF is derived as:

$$e = -\frac{d\psi_{ph}}{dt} \quad (2)$$

With ψ_{ph} , the phase flux linkage comprises the PM flux and the flux generated by the phase current flowing in the windings.

The temperature and the strength of the external magnetic field have a significant role in permanent magnets' magnetic characteristics. Once the PM temperature increases, there is a decrease in both remanence and coercivity, as can be noted in Table III.

TABLE III. THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PMS FOR DIFFERENT OPERATION TEMPERATURES

Temperatures	Coercive Force (A/m)	Residual Flux Density (T)	Relative Permeability
20°C	1,100,000	1	1.05
60°C	800,000	0.95	1.05
100°C	50,000	0.85	1.05
140°C	20,000	0.75	1.05

The decrease in magnetic flux density directly means the PM flux reduction. The decline in PM flux reduces the electromagnetic torque, as indicated in Eq. (1). The impact of PM flux decrease will also be interpreted on the back-EMF RMS value.

In the following sections, the impact of the rise in temperature on the performances of the studied topologies is presented and analysed against the rated condition operation.

A. Rated conditions

Firstly, simulation was performed for each topology at rated conditions: 40.45 A rated current, 4500 rpm rated speed, and 20°C. The RMS values of induced electromotive force (back-EMF) and airgap magnetic flux density (B_δ), as well as the average value of the electromagnetic torque (T_{avg}), torque ripple content (T_{ripple}) and PM magnetic flux density (B_{PM}), are presented in table IV. The induced back-EMF and the electromagnetic torque are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

As mentioned above, no optimisation of the topologies was performed.

Torque ripple content is computed as:

$$T_{ripple(\%)} = \frac{T_{max} - T_{min}}{T_{avg}} \quad (3)$$

Where: T_{max} is the maximum value instantaneous torque; T_{min} is the minimum value instantaneous torque.

TABLE IV. THE MEAN TORQUE, TORQUE RIPPLE, INDUCED EMFs, AND RMS MAGNETIC FLUX DENSITY

Parameters	T_{avg} (N.m)	T_{ripple} (%)	EMF (V)	B_{δ} (T)	B_{PM} (T)	η (%)
SPMSM	4.80	31.7%	27.27	0.66	0.73	94.6
IPMSM	4.75	56.2%	27.45	0.65	0.73	92.6
HPMSM	4.26	51.7%	25.00	0.63	0.71	93.8
SIPMSM	4.09	63.2%	25.70	0.60	0.62	94.0
VIPMSM	3.90	72.2%	21.28	0.56	0.80	91.7

Fig. 3. Torque vs Time for the PMSM Topologies at 20°C

Fig. 4. No Load Induced EMF per Phase versus Time for 5 PMSM Topologies at 20°C.

Table IV and Fig. 3 show that the values of average torque, RMS EMFs, and airgap magnetic flux density for each topology are different due to the position of the PM on the rotors.

The SPMSM has the highest RMS magnetic flux density values in the airgap (0.66 T) and average torque (4.80 N.m), followed by the inlet PM topology. Additionally, the SPMSM has the lowest torque ripple compared to other topologies.

The RMS values and waveforms of back-EMF are different for each case, as shown in Table IV and Fig. 4. According to the design specifications, the DC supply voltage is 72 V, which means that the maximum voltage at the terminal of the stator windings of the PMSM must not exceed 42.5 volts.

TABLE V. EMF HARMONICS MAGNITUDES [V]

	1 st order	3 rd order	5 th order	7 th order	9 th order
SPMSM	38.00	6.42	6.42	0.195	0.13
IPMSM	38.22	5.93	0.43	0.36	0.33
HPMSM	35.28	2.17	0.39	0.17	0.07
SIPMSM	35.40	8.06	0.55	0.22	0.13
VIPMSM	30.05	1.305	0.376	0.065	0.052

The fundamental frequency is 300 Hz. The magnitude values of the back-EMF main harmonic components at 20°C operation temperature are given in Table V.

B. The effects of the temperature change on the motors' performance

Fig. 5-9 and Tables VI-X show the changes in the electromagnetic torque in terms of waveform and average value (see the horizontal dotted lines representing the average value of electromagnetic torque or the values of mean torque on tables) due to the rise in operation temperature. The maximum, minimum, and average torque values, torque ripple content, and magnetic flux density in the airgap and PM are depicted for each topology.

TABLE VI. TORQUE VALUES FOR SPMSM

Temperature	PM at 20°C	PM at 60°C	PM at 100°C	PM at 140°C
Parameters				
T_{max} (Nm)	5.58	5.40	4.78	3.57
T_{min} (Nm)	4.06	3.99	3.63	2.83
T_{avg} (Nm)	4.80	4.68	4.20	3.05
T_{ripple} (%)	31.7%	30.16%	27.20%	25.34%
B_{δ} (T)	0.66	0.63	0.57	0.49
B_{PM} (T)	0.73	0.70	0.64	0.50

Fig. 5. Electromagnetic Torque versus Time of SPMSM topology at 20°C, 60°C, 100°C, and 140°C

TABLE VII. TORQUE VALUES FOR IPMSM

Temperature	PM at 20°C	PM at 60°C	PM at 100°C	PM at 140°C
Parameters				
T_{max} (Nm)	6.09	5.82	5.26	3.70
T_{min} (Nm)	3.42	3.32	3.09	2.02
T_{avg} (Nm)	4.75	4.56	4.16	2.80
T_{ripple} (%)	56.20%	54.74%	52.08%	59.9%
B_{δ} (T)	0.69	0.66	0.60	0.53
B_{PM} (T)	0.73	0.70	0.63	0.45

Fig. 6. Electromagnetic Torque versus Time of IPMSM topology at 20°C, 60°C, 100°C, and 140°C

TABLE VIII. TORQUE VALUES FOR THE HALBACH ROTOR TYPE

Temperature	PM at 20°C	PM at 60°C	PM at 100°C	PM at 140°C
T_{max} (Nm)	5.43	5.16	4.61	3.46
T_{min} (Nm)	3.23	3.15	2.85	2.80
T_{avg} (Nm)	4.26	4.08	3.68	2.52
T_{ripple} (%)	51.70%	48.9%	47.9%	66.07%
B_{δ} (T)	0.63	0.60	0.55	0.48
B_{PM} (T)	0.71	0.67	0.60	0.38

Fig. 7. Electromagnetic Torque versus Time of Halbach topology at 20°C, 60°C, 100°C and 140°C

TABLE IX. TORQUE VALUES FOR THE SPOKE ROTOR TYPE

Temperature	PM at 20°C	PM at 60°C	PM at 100°C	PM at 140°C
T_{max} (Nm)	5.38	5.15	4.67	3.42
T_{min} (Nm)	2.79	2.90	2.53	1.74
T_{avg} (Nm)	4.09	3.91	3.60	2.45
T_{ripple} (%)	63.20%	57.5%	59.51%	68.31%
B_{δ} (T)	0.60	0.57	0.53	0.46
B_{PM} (T)	0.62	0.58	0.53	0.38

It can be noticed that the values of the electromagnetic torque developed by PMSM topologies decrease as the temperature increases (see the values of T_{avg} in Tables VI-X) because the increase in temperature causes the magnet to demagnetise and leads to a decrease in the magnetic flux density (B_{δ}) in the airgap and PM magnetic flux density (B_{PM}).

Fig. 8. Electromagnetic Torque versus Time of Spoke topology at 20°C, 60°C, 100°C and 140°C.

TABLE X. TORQUE VALUES FOR THE V-SHAPE ROTOR TYPE

Temperature	PM at 20°C	PM at 60°C	PM at 100°C	PM at 140°C
T_{max} (Nm)	5.33	5.08	4.59	4.06
T_{min} (Nm)	2.51	2.43	2.24	2.03
T_{avg} (Nm)	3.90	3.73	3.39	3.02
T_{ripple} (%)	72.2%	71.13%	68.9%	67.07%
B_{δ} (T)	0.56	0.54	0.51	0.47
B_{PM} (T)	0.80	0.73	0.63	0.55

Fig. 9. Electromagnetic Torque versus Time of V-shape topology at 20°C, 60°C, 100°C, and 140°C

HPMSM experiences the highest impact of the operation temperature rise on the PM magnetic flux density (almost 47% reduction at 140°C). Moreover, the IPMSM, HPMSM, and SIPMSM experience the highest impact of the operation temperature rise on the average torque (around 40% reduction at 140°C). Consequently, the PM magnetic flux reduction and the average torque correspond to the V-shape topology (31% at 140°C).

The back-EMF is also impacted by the rise of operation temperature (Eq. 2). Fig.10 presents the impact of the topologies working at different temperature values on the back-EMF.

The RMS value of the back-EMF decreases with the operation temperature rise, and for some topologies, changes in harmonics magnitudes can be noticed (See Table XI compared to Table V).

Fig. 100. Back-EMF versus Time at different operation temperatures

Table XI shows the values of back-EMF harmonic magnitudes at 140°C operation temperature and the reduction percentages relative to the same order harmonic magnitudes at 20°C (refer to the values in Table V), given by:

$$\Delta E_v[\%] = \left[1 - \frac{E_{v140^\circ\text{C}}}{E_{v20^\circ\text{C}}} \right] \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

With E_v , the magnitude of the v^{th} harmonic of back-EMF at 20°C and 140°C, respectively.

TABLE XI. HARMONIC MAGNITUDES AT 140°C

		Harmonic order				
		1st	3rd	5th	7th	9th
SPMSM	E_v [V]	27.96	4.07	0.15	0.1	0.08
	ΔE_v [%]	26.42	36.60	97.66	48.72	38.46
IPMSM	E_v [V]	27.79	3.64	0.29	0.24	0.25
	ΔE_v [%]	27.29	38.62	32.56	33.33	24.24
HPMSM	E_v [V]	24.55	0.51	0.16	0.05	0.05
	ΔE_v [%]	30.41	76.50	58.97	70.59	23.74
SIPMSM	E_v [V]	24.98	5.44	0.31	0.15	0.09
	ΔE_v [%]	29.44	32.51	43.64	31.82	30.77
VIPMSM	E_v [V]	21.89	0.99	0.33	0.036	0.04
	ΔE_v [%]	27.15	24.14	12.23	44.62	29.60

It is noticed that, in general, the harmonic magnitudes decrease, but some harmonics experience a higher decrease than others, depending on the machine topology. For SPMSM, the 5th harmonic has a significant reduction (97.66%); for HPMSM, the 3rd and 7th harmonics also have a high decrease (more than 70%).

IV. CONCLUSION

Demagnetisation of PMs occurs when their temperature increases from 20°C to 60°C, 100°C, and 140°C. Based on the results of the analysis, the rise in operation temperature directly impacts the average electromagnetic torque developed by the machine and on the back-EMF. The impact level depends on the rotor topology (i.e., the location of the magnets). Moreover, an impact on the back-EMF harmonics magnitude can be noticed, but only for some of the topologies.

As the temperature rise generates an irreversible decrease in PM characteristics, analysing its impact on the PMSM performances can provide information for problem detection and, further, locating and quantifying the demagnetisation degree.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The funding for this research was provided by the Horizon Europe project titled Network of Excellence in Digital Technologies and AI Solutions for Electromechanical and Power Systems Applications - DITARTIS.

REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Wang, S. Wang, and C. Chen, "Review of sensorless control techniques for PMSM drives," *IEEE Trans. Electr. Electron. Eng.*, vol. 14, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1002/tee.22974.
- [2] H. Wang and J. Leng, "Summary on development of permanent magnet synchronous motor," in *2018 Chinese Control And Decision Conference (CCDC)*, Jun. 2018, pp. 689–693. doi: 10.1109/CCDC.2018.8407219.
- [3] C. Candelo-Zuluaga, A. Garcia Espinosa, J.-R. Riba, and P. T. Blanch, "PMSM Design for Achieving a Target Torque-Speed-Efficiency Map," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 69, no. 12, pp. 14448–14457, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2020.3040313.
- [4] F. Jimenez-Villacorta and L. Lewis, "Advanced Permanent Magnetic Materials," 2014, p. 30.
- [5] S. N. Jani and J. G. Jamnani, "Performance analysis and comparison of PM-Assisted synchronous reluctance motor with ferrites and Rare-earth magnet materials," *Mater. Today Proc.*, vol. 62, pp. 7162–7167, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2022.03.055.
- [6] M. Zhu, "NOVEL METHODS FOR PERMANENT MAGNET DEMAGNETISATION DETECTION IN PERMANENT MAGNET SYNCHRONOUS MACHINES".
- [7] T. Orłowska-Kowalska *et al.*, "Fault Diagnosis and Fault-Tolerant Control of PMSM Drives—State of the Art and Future Challenges," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 59979–60024, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3180153.
- [8] Y. Yu, H. Gao, Q. Chen, P. Liu, and S. Niu, "Demagnetization Fault Detection and Location in PMSM Based on Correlation Coefficient of Branch Current Signals," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 8, Art. no. 8, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/en15082952.
- [9] X. Tang and X. Wang, "Research of the demagnetisation mechanism of line-start permanent magnet synchronous motor under operating condition of sudden reversal," in *2014 17th International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems (ICEMS)*, Oct. 2014, pp. 1981–1984. doi: 10.1109/ICEMS.2014.7013826.